

populations were seeded in 1992 dry season (DS) on 2 Mar to allow segregation for photoperiod sensitivity.

Photoperiod-insensitive and -sensitive plants segregated in a 3:1 ratio, indicating that a single dominant gene

governs photoperiod sensitivity in all three crosses (see table). We classified the segregants that flowered until Aug as photoperiod-insensitive and those that flowered in Sep and later as photoperiod-sensitive. In 1992 WS, desirable

photoperiod-sensitive ms segregants were crossed with respective recurrent parents to get BC₁F₁ generation. The scheme for developing photoperiod-sensitive ms lines is presented in the figure. ■

Isolation of maintainers and restorers for cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines

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We crossed 21 short- and medium-duration indica cultivars with eight CMS lines (see table) during Jul-Oct 1990 to identify maintainers and restorers. F₁ hybrids were grown in the field during Nov 1991-Feb 1992.

Pollen sterility was determined from florets in the upper third of the panicle before dehiscence; pollen grains were stained with I₂-KI. Cultivars with >95% pollen and spikelet sterility were classified as potential maintainers; those

with 5-95%, as partial restorers; and those with <5%, as effective restorers. Maintainers were more frequent than restorers (see table).

IR62829 A/Co 45, IR62829 A/Co 43, IR58025 A/IR50, MS37 A/IET11752, and Mangala A/IR62 had 100% pollen

sterility. These crosses are being used in a backcross program to develop new CMS lines. Co 43, Heera, and MS210 were identified as restorers (see table) and are being used to develop new hybrid combinations. ■

Restorers and maintainers for CMS lines. Coimbatore, India, 1991-92.

CMS line ^a	Potential maintainers	Effective restorers	Partial restorers
IR62829 A (100.0)	Co 43, Co 45	-	ADT36
IR58025 A (99.7)	IR50	Co 43	T2099, 3043, Co 45, IET7511, Aruna
TNAU1 A (99.5)	Co 45, MO 9	Co 43	4308, TM4309, Annada, MO 7
V20 A (100)	TM4309, IR60	-	Co 43
IR46828 A (99.2)	-	Heera	-
MS37 A (99.8)	IR30864, IET11752	MS210	-
IR54755 A (98.9)	IET11752	-	-
Mangala A (99.6)	IR62	-	-

^aFigures in parentheses show spikelet sterility under bagged conditions.

Grain quality

An upland rice line with low protein in Japan

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Polished grain from upland rice, which is high in protein and difficult to process, is used mainly for rice crackers in Japan. Processors have been eager for the development of a lower protein upland rice.

1. Correlation between leaf chlorophyll and grain protein contents in upland rice lines.

2. Correlation between chlorophyll content of leaf and heading period in upland and lowland-upland crossbred rice lines.

We compared the contents of leaf chlorophyll and protein of polished rice in seven lowland-upland crossbred rice lines. These contents were highly correlated ($r = 0.897^{**}$). Selection for leaf chlorophyll content can therefore be

used effectively to breed for grain protein (Fig. 1).

We grew 149 breeding lines of upland, lowland-upland derivatives, and lowland lines cultivated at an Ibaraki upland field in 1992. Chlorophyll content averaged 4.39 mg/100 cm² for upland rice and 4.03 mg/100 cm² for lowland-upland crossbred lines, which were significantly

higher than the 3.73 mg/100 cm² for lowland rice.

A negative correlation was observed between chlorophyll content and days to heading ($r = -0.448^{**}$). Early-maturing lines generally had higher protein content than late-maturing lines, although we found early-maturing lines with lower protein content in lowland-upland

crossbred lines (Fig. 2). We think that the low protein content was inherited from their lowland rice parents, although they have upland rice plant type, are tolerant of drought, and resistant to blast. These lowland-upland crossbred rice lines produce grain that is easy to process for rice crackers. The lines are also resources for breeding. ■

Grain quality of rice harvested at different maturities

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Harvesting rice at optimum maturity is important for obtaining high milling recovery and good cooking quality. We grew six commercial varieties in nonreplicated 600-m² plots during the 1989 and 1990 cropping seasons to study the effect of maturity stage on grain quality. The crop was kept flooded. The 50% flowering date was recorded.

Subplots of 6 m², replicated three times, were harvested from 27 to 42 d after flowering (DAF) at intervals of 3 d. Samples were sun-dried and milled 2 mo after harvest using Satake Rice Husking Machine Model THU-35A and Burrows McGill Polisher No. 3. Milled whole grains were cooked in excess water.

Grain maturity stage greatly affected rice quality (see table). We observed high total milled rice and head rice recovery with more elongation and less bursting/curling of grains upon cooking when the crop was harvested at 20-23% moisture. This level coincides with 33-36 DAF in all of the varieties except Basmati 198, which took 39 d.

Head rice recovery was low at both early and late maturity stages. Total milled rice and elongation ratio and bursting/curling upon cooking improved with delay in harvesting date up to 20-23% moisture, after which they leveled off. ■

Effect of harvesting rice at different stages of maturity on grain quality. RRI, Kala Shah Kaku, Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan. 1989 and 1990.^a

Days to harvesting after 50% flowering	Moisture at harvest (%)	Milled rice recovery (% of rough rice dry weight)		Elongation ratio on cooking	Bursting/curling upon cooking (%)
		Total milled rice	Head rice		
27	27.8	68.02 c	49.62 d	1.702 d	11.90 a
30	25.3	69.13 b	52.75 bc	1.798 c	10.27 b
33	22.9	70.18 a	54.48 a	1.860 b	9.02 c
36	20.3	70.40 a	54.62 a	1.900 ab	8.38 cd
39	17.9	70.42 a	53.75 ab	1.908 ab	8.27 d
42	15.5	70.28 a	51.87 c	1.913 a	8.25 d
CV (%)	-	0.7	2.7	2.3	6.5
LSD (0.05)	-	0.59	1.71	0.05	0.72

^aMeans in a column followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Relationship of Basmati 370 grain quality to soil and environment

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We conducted a pot experiment to study how soil and environment affect quality attributes and aroma development in Basmati 370. The crop was grown at Daska, a traditional rice-growing area, and Multan, a nontraditional rice-growing area of southern Punjab, during 1989 and 1990 dry seasons. See table for treatments. We evaluated the samples 3 mo after harvest.

Values for kernel length and length:breadth ratio were high in the Daska soil and environment sample (see table). Protein content was about the same across treatments. All samples had intermediate amylose and gelatinization temperature. Elongation and volume expansion ratios upon cooking were highest and aroma strongest in rice from Daska soil and environment. Aroma was

very poor in some samples and absent in the rice from Multan soil and environment.

We can conclude that rice from Daska soil and environment was better in cooked-rice cohesiveness and aroma than were any of the other samples. Aroma is the result of soil, environment, and plant type interaction. ■

IRRN REMINDER

Routine research. Reports of screening trials of varieties, fertilizer, cropping methods, and other routine observations using standard methodologies to establish local recommendations are not accepted. Examples are single-season, single-trial field experiments. All field trials should be repeated across more than one season, in multiple seasons, or in more than one location as appropriate. All experiments should include replications and an internationally known check or control treatment.